

DEVELOPMENT OF LEARNING GUIDE IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP (BUSINESS PLAN): BASIS FOR AN ENHANCED ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCIES

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ABSTRACT

Although there are obvious benefits, various researches still find the implementation of entrepreneurship in schools. Special programs, including entrepreneurship may further issue supplementary guidelines in relation to the program's specific assessment concerns. This paper aims to address this gap by compiling a toolkit for entrepreneurship educators aspiring to design and implement K-12 curriculum competencies. To find out the output of the research study, the researcher adopted a questionnaire to describe and gather information from the respondents to determine their entrepreneurial competencies. Data were tested using different statistical tools such as frequency, mean, standard deviation and Spearman correlation. Among the PEC (Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies), the students perceived that they were able to: 1) do the ability of successful entrepreneurs to get thing done successfully, typically by effort, courage, or skill, 2) do the ability of successful entrepreneurs to process thinking about the activities required to achieve the desired goal in the future, and 3) do a manager's ability to influence others in the future. More importantly, it was found out that there is a significant difference in Developing a Business Plan when the respondents are grouped according to Strand. This means that the students were able to develop a business plan in their exposure with the K-12 curriculum. Subsequently, there is a significant difference in Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies when the respondents are grouped according to Strand. This shows that the students realize the personal entrepreneurial competencies in relevance to their classes.

Keywords: K-12 Curriculum, Entrepreneurship, Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies